

Evaluation of Tensile Properties and Water Absorption of Abaca Fiber Thermoplastic Composite Relative to the Fiber Length, Type of Matrix and Nanoprecipitated Calcium Carbonate

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Abstract

The high costs of synthetic fibers and the demands for environment – friendly materials led to the search for new reinforcing materials that are inexpensive and biodegradable. A viable substitute are natural fibers, particularly abaca which is abundant and locally harvested, lighter, and ecological. This work presents the mechanical properties and water uptake behavior of woven, short, and flour abaca fibers, reinforcing high density polyethylene (HDPE) and linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE) composites. Effects to the mechanical properties of alkali pretreatment (NaOH) of the fibers, incorporating the matrix with nanoprecipitated calcium carbonate (NPCC), and use of a coupling agent (maleic anhydride) to the fibers were also observed. Effect of different matrices was also conducted. The composites were prepared by using a two-roll mill followed by compression molding. Mechanical testing were done using a universal testing machine, and water absorption was conducted following the ASTM D570 standards. Results showed that alkali treatment and use of maleic anhydride improved the mechanical properties, due to an enhanced fiber surface adhesion with the matrix. Woven fibers remained the strongest reinforcing material due to higher fiber length. Addition of 1% by wt of NPCC increased the mechanical strength and reduced the water absorption. Due to different molecular structure of polyethylene, LLDPE exhibited low mechanical strength and low water resistance.

Introduction

Abaca

- Scientifically known as *Musa textilis Nee*
- worldwide known as **Manila Hemp**
- Abaca fiber is one of the strongest natural fibers, locally abundant, resistant against rotting; exhibits high flexural strength, comparable to that of glass fiber, and good abrasion resistance, dampness and excellent resistance from UV rays

Objective:

To fabricate abaca fiber reinforced composites and evaluate its mechanical properties

Significance:

Body parts of automotive and aircrafts made from Abaca FRCs

Methodology

Characterization

- Mechanical Properties
- Water absorption
- Morphology

Results

Mechanical properties of Polyethylene-abaca flour composites

Figure 1. Effect of different matrices on the mechanical properties of abaca flour reinforced composite (A), percent elongation at break (B), tensile modulus (C), and flexural strength (D).

Mechanical Properties of Varying Abaca Fiber Length and with NPCC

Figure 2. Effect of Varying fiber length on the mechanical properties of abaca fiber reinforced composite (A), percent elongation at break (B), tensile modulus (C), and flexural strength (D).

Figure 3. Effect of NPCC loading on the mechanical properties of abaca woven fiber reinforced composite in terms of tensile strength (A), percent elongation at break (B), tensile modulus (C), and flexural strength (D).

Results

Water Absorption

Figure 4. Water absorption curves of abaca woven fiber composite with effect of increasing (A) HDPE/abaca flour composite (B), abaca flour-LLDPE (C), short abaca fiber/HDPE composites (d) HDPE-abaca fabric with NPCC loading

Figure 4. SEM images of PE/abaca flour composites and HDPE/abaca fabric with NPCC

Conclusion

- Addition of coupling agent maleic anhydride in the system further improved the mechanical properties of the composites. Water uptake was also improved. This was due to better adhesion between the fibers and matrix.
- Incorporation of abaca woven fabric improved the tensile strength of pure HDPE. Further improvement in alkali (NaOH) treated abaca fibers were observed.
- 1% NPCC led to an increase in the tensile strength and modulus. The presence of NPCC reduced the composite's water absorption.
- Woven fabrics exhibited the strongest mechanical properties, followed by milled fibers, and lastly the short fibers. Abaca flour exceeded the short fibers due to higher aspect ratio, less imperfections per fiber unit, and achieving the critical fiber length.
- LLDPE – abaca flour exhibited low mechanical strength than HDPE- abaca flour due to different molecular structure of the matrix.